

TEACHERS' EMOTIONAL AVAILABILITY, STORYTELLING PRACTICES AND HOME LITERACY ECOLOGY: IMPLICATIONS ON KINDERGARTNERS' ORAL NARRATIVE SKILLS

Paoline Antonette M. Convicto, Revina O. Mendoza

*Graduate School, Lourdes College Inc., Cagayan de Oro City,
Misamis Oriental Philippines*

ABSTRACT

Oral narrative skills are important in early childhood education for language development and literacy learning. Grounded in Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), which emphasizes the role of social interaction and guided learning in language development, this study aimed to determine the influence of teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, and home literacy ecology (HLE) on kindergartners' oral narrative skills in the local context. A descriptive-correlational design was employed involving 163 kindergartners from a district in Misamis Oriental for the school year 2025-2026. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula, and the participants were selected using simple random sampling. Data were collected using adapted and researcher-made questionnaires and rubrics that were validated by experts and underwent Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, canonical correlation, and multiple regression analysis. Results showed generally high levels of emotional availability, storytelling practices, and HLE. However, kindergartners showed only a generally fair level of oral narrative skills. Data revealed that teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, and HLE significantly influenced kindergartners' oral narrative skills. Storytelling practices and emotional availability significantly predicted children's ability to express and organize ideas. The study highlights the importance of positive teacher-child interactions, engaging storytelling strategies, and enriched home literacy environments in developing young learners' oral language skills, which may help educators and parents support early literacy development. Future researchers may explore other factors that may influence children's oral narrative skills.

Keywords: *Oral Narrative Skills, Emotional Availability, Storytelling Practices, Home Literacy Ecology, Kindergarten Learners, Early Literacy*

INTRODUCTION

Oral narrative is an important component of young children's language and literacy acquisition. Children learn to tell stories, describe events, and present ideas in a logical sequence, which aids vocabulary development, comprehension, and subsequent success in reading and writing. The oral narrative skills that kindergarten students develop are an important resource for their success in school, since they will use oral communication to share their ideas, experiences, and understanding in formal and informal settings throughout the school day.

Globally, oral narrative development has become an important concern in early childhood education because many young learners experience difficulties in organizing ideas, sequencing events, and expressing thoughts clearly during oral interactions. Researchers and educators worldwide recognize that strong oral language abilities are essential foundations for literacy development and academic achievement. One important area of study in applied linguistics and language acquisition is how preschoolers develop their oral narrative skills (Li, 2025). Emotional availability is an important factor in the classroom. Research has shown that teacher emotional support significantly enhances students' self-efficacy, resilience, and classroom engagement, highlighting the value of emotionally supportive teacher–student interactions in promoting positive learning outcomes. (Quan et al., 2025). Teachers who are emotionally available create a safe environment in which to express oneself. Children enjoy story time activities, which develop their sense of story by engaging them in supportive interactions, enabling their participation in conversation, and encouraging them to speak confidently.

Teachers' storytelling is another important determining factor in kindergartners' oral narrative skills. Storytelling, especially when integrated with interactive activities like games, enhances children's involvement and interest in learning, rendering it a beneficial pedagogical approach in early childhood education (Ratih et al., 2022). It is an approach to early childhood practice that provides children with relevant opportunities to listen to, understand, and generate narratives. Children are developing the skills to recognize the structure of effective storytelling and to present ideas clearly. Storytelling techniques, including encouraging predictions, allowing re-storying, asking open-ended questions, and engaging in conversations with children, help structure the story, sequence events, and foster expressive language.

The children's home literacy environment is also an important factor influencing oral language development, alongside classroom influences. Home literacy ecology has been identified as a significant predictor of young children's future language and literacy learning (Goodrich et al., 2021). Children exposed to diverse experiences with literary information are more likely to have a better vocabulary, a better understanding of narrative, and a greater aesthetic appreciation of verbal expression at home. Children's

overall narrative and language growth result from interactions between home and school literacy experiences. In the Philippines, the MATATAG Kindergarten Curriculum of the Department of Education places strong emphasis on developing the foundational literacy and numeracy aspects of the developmentally appropriate learning experiences. A focus on oral language development and communication, and on their importance in early learning, supports children's emergent literacy and readiness for formal education. Emergent literacy includes the skills related to oral language (listening, speaking, and vocabulary development), print awareness (understanding letters, words, and printed text), alphabet knowledge (identifying and naming letters), and phonological awareness (recognizing and manipulating sounds in words). Of these, the abilities in the domain of oral language are important bases from which children learn storytelling, an ability studied in this research. Oral language experiences, such as stories and shared reading, promote children's comprehension and representation of ideas.

This research is in line with MATATAG Kindergarten Curriculum which aimed to develop oral language and emergent literacy skills which will create for the learners the continuity of transition to formal education in the elementary level (Department of Education [DepEd], 2023). In the local context, the researcher observed that many kindergartners in the school where the study was conducted experience difficulty organizing their thoughts and ideas clearly during classroom discussions and storytelling activities. Some learners use incomplete sentences, while others are unable to present events in a logical order. During story-sharing sessions, some children forget important story details, making their narratives difficult to understand. These classroom observations indicate the need to examine factors that may contribute to the development of kindergartners' oral narrative skills.

There are few empirical studies documenting how these three factors are simultaneously related to children's oral narrative skills. These are observed by teachers to affect children's oral narratives not only singly but also in combination as they interact in everyday classroom activities, particularly for children with limited literacy experiences at home. This indicates the need for further research to understand how these three factors contribute to the development of oral narrative skills in authentic contexts. This gap underscores the need to examine how teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, and home literacy ecology influence kindergartners' oral narrative skills. Specifically, this study aims to determine the extent to which these three factors contribute to children's ability to sequence events, recognize story structure, use vocabulary, and express ideas through language. By examining these variables together, the study seeks to provide a clearer understanding of the school and home factors that support the development of oral narrative skills among kindergartners.

This study aligns with Goal 4: Quality Education of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Target 4.2, which aims to ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care, and pre-primary education. By exploring the relationships among teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, home literacy ecology, and kindergartners' oral narrative skills, this study seeks to

contribute to improving early literacy development as a foundation for equitable and inclusive quality education and lifelong learning.

Research Questions

This study sought to investigate teachers' emotional availability, teachers' storytelling practices, and kindergartners' home literacy ecology as implications of kindergartners' oral narrative skills in schools in a district of Misamis Oriental for the school year 2025–2026. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the kindergartners' assessment of their teachers' emotional availability in terms of:
 - 1.1 sensitivity;
 - 1.2 structuring;
 - 1.3 non-intrusiveness; and
 - 1.4 non-hostility?
2. What is the kindergartners' assessment of their teachers' storytelling practices in terms of:
 - 2.1 voice;
 - 2.2 facial expression; and
 - 2.3 body language?
3. What is the kindergartners' level of home literacy ecology?
4. What is the kindergartners' level of oral narrative skills considering:
 - 4.1. sequencing;
 - 4.2. story structure awareness;
 - 4.3. vocabulary; and
 - 4.4. language use?
5. Are the teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices and home literacy ecology significantly associated with the kindergartners' oral narrative skills?
6. Do teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, and home literacy ecology significantly influence the kindergartners' oral narrative skills?

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational design. As described by Bhandari (2021), this research design helped measure the relationships among variables and enabled informed predictions based on the identified relationships. Hence, this research examined the influence of teachers' emotional availability, teachers' storytelling practices, and kindergartners' home literacy ecology on kindergartners' oral narrative skills; therefore, the descriptive-correlational research design was deemed appropriate.

The study included kindergartners aged 5 to 7 years who were officially enrolled in the 2025–2026 school year, totaling 276 learners. These served as the study's inclusion criteria. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula with a 5% margin

of error, resulting in 163 participants. This level of precision was chosen to provide adequate representation of the population while retaining statistical reliability. The participants were selected through simple random sampling, giving each learner an equal chance of being included in the study.

The exclusion criteria included learners who were below 5 years old or above 7 years old, were not officially enrolled in the 2025–2026 school year or were absent during the data collection period.

The instruments utilized to collect data in this study were survey questionnaire and a rubric. To determine the teachers' emotional availability, this study adapted the Emotional Availability Questionnaire from Busalla and Mendoza (2024). Selected items were reworded for clarity, age appropriateness and to better fit the context of this study.

The Teacher Storytelling Practices Questionnaire was developed by the researcher to measure classroom storytelling behaviors related to expressive voice, facial expression, and body language. The items were initially informed by evidence showing that expressive storytelling behaviors enhance children's engagement and comprehension (Vieta & Nhib, 2024). Through storytelling, children continuously use language to construct and convey narratives, which supports their language development (Hasanah et al., 2022; Nishonova, 2021).

Home Literacy Ecology Questionnaire was a modified version of the Home Literacy Environment Questionnaire (Buvaneswari & Padakannaya, 2017). The original questionnaire had five dimensions that focused on the home literacy environment. To be responsive to the broader concept of home literacy ecology, this study's instrument included items that encompassed the presence of literacy materials, family interactions, routines, and support for literacy. The chosen items were grouped and analyzed as a whole to provide an overall picture of kindergartners' home literacy ecology. Items that did not relate to the research aims were excluded, and those in hand were adapted to fit the context of the kindergartners.

A researcher-created rubric was used to evaluate kindergartners' oral narrative skills. The rubric was designed to assess children's storytelling performance on the following four criteria: story sequencing, awareness of story structure, vocabulary, and use of language. The story structure awareness dimension is part of the oral narrative skills rubric because it is important for kindergartners to be able to name and discuss the key parts of a story, such as the characters, setting, events, and resolution. Studies indicate that retelling activities have a significant impact on young children's knowledge of aspects of story grammar, helping them develop more complex, well-structured oral narratives (Vretudaki, 2021). This helps validate the evaluation of story structure awareness as a component of oral narrative competence in young children. At the same time, language use, including vocabulary, is added to the oral narrative skills rubric since research has demonstrated that children's vocabulary and grammar skills are reliable predictors of the quality and coherence of their oral narrative (Khan et al., 2021).

Content validation and reliability tests were conducted for the instruments used in the study, and the instruments were reviewed by field experts and panel members. Their comments and suggestions were incorporated into the research instruments. The pilot test was conducted with participants from another class that did not take part in the study but shared the same characteristics as the study participants. The research instruments of teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, home literacy ecology, and kindergartners' oral narrative skills were piloted on the thirty (30) kindergartners. The children in these kindergartens were not part of the study.

Moreover, the researcher used Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient to determine the internal consistency of the items. A coefficient value of 0.70 or higher was acceptable in this study. The reliability test results showed that the instruments had good internal consistency. For Teachers' Emotional Availability, the Cronbach's alphas were 0.705 for sensitivity, 0.702 for structuring, 0.727 for non-intrusiveness, and 0.724 for non-hostility. Alpha values for Teachers' Storytelling Practices were 0.797 for Voice, 0.725 for Facial expression, and 0.700 for Body language. The Home Literacy Ecology questionnaire had an alpha of 0.716, and the rubric for Oral Narrative Skills had an alpha of 0.907. All the coefficients were above the acceptable level of 0.70, which showed that the instruments were reliable for use in the study.

The analysis in the study began with a CFA (Confirmatory Factor Analysis), for the construct validity of the measured variables. The factor structures of Voice (7 items), Facial Expression (8 items), and Body Language (8 items) were assessed using CFA. The best fit CFA model of the three constructs is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) Best-fit Model of Voice, Facial Expression, and Body Language

Legend: V = Voice, F = Facial Expression, B = Body Language

After evaluating factor loadings and model fit, three items were retained for both V and B, and five for F. This ensured that the observed items adequately reflected their respective latent constructs and that the model achieved acceptable fit to the data. All latent variables were represented by their retained indicators, and the standardized factor loadings ranged from 0.27 to 0.77, indicating moderate to strong relationships between the indicators and their latent variables. The correlations among the latent constructs were also examined, revealing meaningful relationships that support the conceptual framework. The model fit was evaluated using multiple indices, including CMIN/DF, Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and PClose.

Table 1 shows the estimates, cutoff criteria, and interpretation for each index. The fit indices indicate that the CFA model fits the data well. Cmin/df, RMSEA, and PClose indicate excellent fit, while CFI and SRMR fall within acceptable ranges. These results support the construct validity of the measured variables. The finalized CFA model established construct validity and provided a solid foundation for subsequent analyses, including regression and predictive modeling.

Table 1
Model Fit Indices

Index	Estimate	Cut-off Criterion	Interpretation
Cmin/df	1.409	Between 0 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.900	≥0.90	Acceptable
SRMR	0.074	≤0.08	Acceptable
RMSEA	0.050	<.08	Excellent
PClose	0.472	>0.05	Excellent

Note. Cmin/df = Minimum Discrepancy divided by Degrees of Freedom; CFI = Comparative Fit Index; SRMR = Standardized Root Mean Square Residual; RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; PClose = Probability of Close Fit. Source: Hu and Bentler (1999), "Cutoff Criteria for Fit Indexes in Covariance Structure Analysis"

The following scoring guidelines guided the researcher in the analysis of data:

For Teachers' Emotional Availability, Storytelling Practices and Home Literacy Ecology

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
5	4.51 - 5.00	Always	Very High Extent
4	3.51- 4.50	Often	High Extent
3	2.51 - 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate Extent
2	1.51- 2.50	Rarely	Low Extent
1	1.00 -1.50	Never	Very Low Extent

A rubric with four criteria (sequencing, story structure awareness, vocabulary, and language use) was used to evaluate the oral narrative skills of the kindergartners. The rating scale for each criterion ranged from 1 to 5, with 1 being the lowest and 5 the highest. The mean score for each criterion and the overall mean score were calculated to decide

the overall level of oral narrative skills. The mean scores were subsequently analyzed at the following performance levels:

For Kindergartners’ Oral Narrative Skills

<i>Range</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Performance Level</i>
4.51 – 5.00	Outstanding	Advanced
3.51 – 4.50	Very good	Proficient
2.51 – 3.50	Good	Approaching Proficiency
1.51 – 2.50	Fair	Developing
1.00 – 1.50	Poor	Beginning

The overall mean score reflects the kindergartners’ level of oral narrative skills, including sequencing, story structure awareness, vocabulary, and language use.

RESULTS

The following are the results of the study.

Table 2
Summary Table of the Kindergartners’ Assessment of their Teachers’ Emotional Availability

Teachers’ Emotional Availability	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sensitivity	3.48	0.71	Moderate Extent
Structuring	3.80	0.66	High Extent
Non-intrusiveness	3.77	0.73	High Extent
Non-hostility	3.91	0.67	High Extent
Overall	3.74	0.60	High Extent

Table 3
Summary Table of the Kindergartners’ Assessment of their Teachers’ Storytelling Practices

Teachers’ Storytelling Practices	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Voice	3.88	0.74	High Extent
Facial Expression	3.72	0.64	High Extent
Body Language	3.73	0.76	High Extent
Overall	3.78	0.56	High Extent

Table 4
Descriptive Statistics of Kindergartners' Home Literacy Ecology

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51 – 5.00	Always	Very High Extent	9	5.52
3.51 – 4.50	Often	High Extent	75	46.01
2.51 – 3.50	Sometimes	Moderate Extent	58	35.58
1.51 – 2.50	Rarely	Low Extent	21	12.88
1.00 – 1.50	Never	Very Low Extent	0	0.00
Total			163	100
Mean			3.44	
SD			0.65	
Interpretation			Moderate Extent	

Table 5
Summary Table of the Kindergartners' Overall Level of Oral Narrative Skills

Oral Narrative Skills	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Sequencing	2.16	0.73	Fair
Story Structure Awareness	2.24	0.68	Fair
Vocabulary	2.14	0.69	Fair
Language Use	2.10	0.69	Fair
Overall	2.16	0.89	Fair

Table 6
Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Teachers' Emotional Availability and Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R _c	R _c ²	F(16, 474)	p
Emotional Availability					
Sensitivity	-0.42				
Structuring	-0.31				
Non-Intrusiveness	-0.32				
Non-Hostility	-0.37	0.45	0.20	2.951*	<.001
Oral Narrative Skills					
Sequencing	-0.17				
Story Structure Awareness	-0.12				
Vocabulary	0.09				
Language Use	0.13				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Table 7
Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Story Telling Practices and Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R _c	R _c ²	F(12, 413)	p
Story Telling Practices					
Voice	-0.33				
Facial Expression	-0.20				
Body Language	-0.27				
Oral Narrative Skills		0.36	0.13	2.062*	0.018
Sequencing	-0.06				
Story Structure Awareness	0.01				
Vocabulary	0.16				
Language Use	0.18				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Table 8
Canonical Correlation Analysis Between Home Literacy Ecology and Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills

Variable	Cross loading	R _c	R _c ²	F(4, 158)	p
Home Literacy Ecology	0.30				
Oral Narrative Skills					
Sequencing	0.29	0.30	0.09	3.778*	0.006
Story Structure Awareness	0.28				
Vocabulary	0.24				
Language Use	0.21				

*Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.

Table 9
Regression Analysis of Teachers' Emotional Availability, Storytelling Practices, and Home Literacy Ecology on Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills

Predictor	Unstandardized Coefficients		β	95% CI		t	p
	B	SE		Lower	Upper		
Constant	6.49	0.58		3.37	9.60	4.11	<.001
Emotional Availability	0.49	0.40	0.113	-0.31	1.29	1.21	0.228
Storytelling Practices	-1.20*	0.46	-0.261	-2.10	-0.30	-2.64	0.009
Home Literacy Ecology	1.41*	0.32	0.354	0.78	2.04	4.44	<.001

Model Summary

$R = 0.342$ $R^2 = 0.117$ $\text{Adjusted } R^2 = 0.101$ $F(3,159) = 7.04^*$ $p < .001$

*Note. B = unstandardized beta coefficient, SE = standard error, β = standardized beta coefficient, 95% CI = 95% confidence interval, t = t statistic, p = probability value. *Significant at 0.05 two-tailed alpha level.*

DISCUSSION

Table 2 presents the summary of the components of teachers' emotional availability. The result revealed that teachers demonstrate a high extent of kindness toward their kindergartners, as shown in an overall mean of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 0.60. The data imply that most kindergartners perceive their teachers as supportive and responsive in classroom interactions.

These findings are supported by research showing that emotional availability involves teachers' capacity to provide warmth, structure, autonomy support, and responsive interactions that help children feel secure and valued in the classroom. When teachers interact in a calm and respectful manner, children experience greater emotional security and engagement, which contribute to their socio-emotional development (Garcia-Peinado, 2023). Similarly, positive and supportive teacher–student relationships promote children's emotional well-being, and engagement contributing to a more supportive classroom setting (Wang, 2023).

Table 3 shows that kindergartners rated their teachers' storytelling practices to a high extent, as shown in the summary with an overall mean of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 0.56. According to the data, teachers exhibit a high level of effective use of voice, with a mean score of 3.88, while the use of facial expressions is associated with the lowest mean score of 3.72, though it is still interpreted as high.

These findings are supported by Simatupang et al. (2025), who concluded that improvements in storytelling delivery, particularly through expressive voice and visual cues, played a critical role in fostering children's engagement and comprehension during storytelling activities. This aligns with the data, where teachers' use of voice was rated highest, while facial expressions, though slightly lower, still demonstrate effective storytelling practices. Similarly, expressive storytelling techniques such as vocal changes, facial expressions, gestures, and dramatic delivery have been shown to enhance children's emotional engagement and understanding of story content by supporting their recall of characters' feelings and emotions during storytelling activities (van Huisstede et al., 2026).

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics for home literacy ecology ratings by the kindergartners. The result revealed that kindergartners' level of home literacy ecology is high, as shown in the overall mean of 3.44 and a standard deviation of 0.65. The data imply that many kindergartners experience supportive literacy interactions in their home environment. This implies that kindergartners who are often exposed to literacy-related experiences at home, such as listening to stories, looking at books, engaging in conversations with family members, and participating in reading or writing activities.

These findings are consistent with research showing that a supportive home literacy environment contributes to positive reading attitudes and literacy development among children (Claes et al., 2024). A supportive home environment plays a key role in the development of young learners' learning skills (Busalla & Mendoza, 2024).

Table 5 presents the summary of the kindergartners' overall level of oral narrative skills. The results reveal that the overall mean score is 2.16 with a standard deviation of 0.89, which is interpreted as fair. This indicates that the kindergartners are at the developing level in their oral narrative skills.

This means that the learners are beginning to demonstrate basic skills in organizing events, understanding story structure, using appropriate vocabulary, and expressing ideas through simple sentences. Similarly, oral narrative development in early childhood involves children's emerging ability to organize story events coherently, apply vocabulary meaningfully, and express ideas through structured language during storytelling and classroom interactions (Xing et al., 2025).

Table 6 shows the canonical correlation analysis between Teachers' Emotional Availability and Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills. The result revealed a significant canonical correlation between Teachers' Emotional Availability and Oral Narrative Skills, $F(16, 474) = 2.951, p < .001, R_c = 0.45, R_c^2 = 0.20$. This indicates that the first canonical function explained 20% of the shared variance between teachers' emotional availability and kindergartners' oral narrative skills, suggesting a moderate relationship between the two sets of variables. Since the canonical correlation was found to be statistically significant, the first null hypothesis is rejected. The results suggest that teachers' emotional availability is associated with children's oral narrative development.

This finding supports the idea that emotionally supportive teacher-child interactions play an important role in children's language development. Emotionally available interactions, characterized by warmth, responsiveness, and supportive communication, create learning environments that promote children's language development, and active participation in classroom interactions (Yang et al., 2021).

Table 7 shows the canonical correlation analysis between Storytelling Practices and Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills. The result revealed that there is a significant canonical correlation between Storytelling Practices and Oral Narrative Skills, $F(12, 413) = 2.062, p = 0.018, R_c = 0.36, R_c^2 = 0.13$. This indicates that about 13 percent of the variability in Oral Narrative Skills is explained by Storytelling Practices. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is rejected. The result suggests that teachers' storytelling behaviors are associated with children's oral narrative development.

This finding supports previous research suggesting that storytelling activities provide meaningful opportunities for children to develop language and narrative abilities. According to Nicolopoulou et al. (2021), storytelling and narrative activities in early childhood classrooms help children practice organizing ideas, expressing thoughts, and developing language skills that support narrative competence.

Table 8 shows the canonical correlation analysis between Home Literacy Ecology and Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills. The result revealed that there is a significant canonical correlation between Home Literacy Ecology and Oral Narrative Skills, $F(4, 158) = 3.778$, $p = 0.006$, $R_c = 0.30$, $R_c^2 = 0.09$. This indicates that about 9 percent of the variability in Oral Narrative Skills is explained by Home Literacy Ecology. Therefore, the third null hypothesis is rejected. The result suggests that the literacy environment at home is associated with children's oral narrative development.

This finding supports previous research suggesting that children's exposure to books, storytelling, and language interactions at home plays an important role in the development of their language and narrative skills. According to Dowdall et al. (2020), home literacy experiences, such as shared reading and conversations about stories, help strengthen children's vocabulary, language development, and narrative abilities.

Table 9 presents the multiple regression analysis predicting Kindergartners' Oral Narrative Skills from Teachers' Emotional Ability, Storytelling Practices, and Home Literacy Ecology. The overall model was statistically significant, $F(3, 159) = 7.04$, $p < .001$, with $R = 0.342$, $R^2 = 0.117$, and $\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.101$. Therefore, the fourth null hypothesis can be rejected. The finding that teachers' emotional availability, storytelling practices, and home literacy ecology significantly influence kindergartners' oral narrative skills suggests that both classroom and home environments play crucial roles in early language development.

This finding is supported by recent literature showing that the quality of children's classroom and home language environments contributes to their language development. Rankin et al. (2022) found that the emotional quality of early education programs improves children's language learning, suggesting that emotionally supportive classrooms help foster language growth. Likewise, shared storybook reading has been identified as an important source of oral language development in both home and child-care contexts (Grolig, 2020). In addition, Niklas et al. (2020) found that the home literacy environment significantly predicts children's linguistic competencies, highlighting the value of literacy experiences at home. Together, these studies support the present finding that teachers' emotional availability, storytelling-related classroom practices, and home literacy ecology influence kindergartners' oral narrative skills.

Conclusions

The results of this study show that the classroom and home environments are important factors in the development of kindergartners' oral narrative skills. The results indicate that oral language is well developed when children have positive teacher-child relationships, many literacy-rich activities and a positive home literacy environment. These contexts combine to give children opportunities to structure, present, and communicate a story effectively.

The results also underscore the importance of interactive and child-centered practices. Although storytelling is used in classrooms, for it to be effective, it needs to

involve children's active participation, retelling, and discussion. In the same way, moderate home literacy activities suggest that the more meaningful and active parents are at home, the more frequently they occur, and the more they could support narrative skills, underscoring the importance of teacher and parent collaboration.

Lastly, emotional support may foster a safe learning environment and be nurturing, but this alone will not directly improve oral narrative skills. The results highlight the importance of integrating the three factors (emotional availability, high-quality interactive storytelling, and enriched home literacy experiences) to support and maximize oral language development, providing a solid foundation for subsequent literacy and academic achievement.

The results of this study support Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Learning (1978), which suggests that children's language and cognitive growth are a product of meaningful social interactions with more knowledgeable others. The strong correlation between teachers' emotional availability and storytelling and kindergartners' oral narrative skills highlights that children's narrative competence is not an individual learning process but is developed with the teachers' guidance and scaffolding in the classroom. Further, the importance of home literacy ecology underscores the value of social interaction with parents and/or caregivers, which continues to reinforce children's development of oral language, reiterating the idea that interaction is a key mechanism in early learning.

The study's findings also support Nel Noddings' Caring Theory (1984), which emphasizes the importance of caring and supportive relationships in the learning process. The high extent of teachers' emotional availability, particularly in terms of sensitivity, structuring, non-intrusiveness, and non-hostility, reflects the role of caring teacher-child interactions in creating a safe and nurturing classroom environment. These supportive relationships encourage children to participate confidently in storytelling and oral communication activities, which contribute to the development of their oral narrative skills. The findings suggest that when teachers demonstrate warmth, patience, and responsiveness, children become more engaged and comfortable expressing their ideas and narratives.

The study is also related to Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979), which states that the child is surrounded by various interrelated systems, such as microsystems, home, and school. The results of the combined influence of classroom practices and home literacy experiences on oral narrative skills illustrate the interplay between different levels of children's environments and how this influences children's learning. This highlights the importance of both school-based interventions and support at home, as Bronfenbrenner saw development as the result of children's interactions with their environments and social contexts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions in the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

1. For School Administrators to consider enhancing the delivery of training and workshops for teachers, focusing on effective storytelling strategies and language development activities for young learners, as well as fostering development among public school pupils through regular school-based learning action cells (SLAC), INSET, and other professional growth and development methods, ultimately improving teachers' teaching competences for the benefit of learners.
2. For Kindergarten Teachers to continue using expressive and engaging storytelling strategies in the classroom. They may also provide more opportunities for children to practice retelling stories and to share their own experiences, thereby improving their oral narrative skills.
3. For Parents to support their children's literacy development at home by reading storybooks, telling stories, and engaging in simple conversations with their children regularly. These activities can help strengthen the child's language and storytelling abilities.
4. For Future Researchers to conduct similar studies with a larger group of participants or explore other factors that may influence children's oral narrative skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Approval for this study was obtained from the school's Research Ethics Committee (REC). Ethical clearance obtained, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to survey the participants through the district supervisor, the school principal, and the kindergarten teachers. Prior to performing the study at the school site, written permission from the principal was also obtained. The researcher adopted the ethical principles laid out by The Belmont Report (National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979), which include Respect for Persons, Beneficence, and Justice, in conducting research. Protecting participants' rights to their information and its confidentiality and securing informed consent from parents and informed assent from participants, ensured respect for participants. Beneficence was demonstrated by minimizing potential harms, ensuring that participants were protected from harm, and by the study's benefits for educational practice. A fair selection of participants and equal treatment of all participants of this study have been done to ensure justice.

The researcher emphasized to the participants that their participation was purely voluntary. Considering the age of the kindergartners', informed assent was secured from their parents or legal guardians. There are no penalties if parents or legal guardians decide to remove their child from the study at any time. A learner may discontinue participation at any moment if they are uncomfortable or decide they do not want to continue. The learner's decision to withdraw will not affect their position at school or their treatment in any way. Confidentiality of all information and data was strictly maintained throughout the study, including the protection of the kindergartners' identifying information. Electronic data were stored on a password-protected computer, which only

researcher will have access to, while hard copies will be kept in a locked cabinet. All data will be kept for five years for academic purposes, after which all electronic files will be permanently deleted, and hard copies will be disposed of properly. No participant's identity was divulged in the study or in any reporting. The researcher declared that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study. No financial, professional, or personal interests influenced the study methods, analysis, or interpretation of the findings.

After the completion of the study, the findings were shared with the concerned stakeholders to support professional development and improve educational practices while ensuring the confidentiality of all participants. The manuscript also underwent plagiarism and AI detection checks as required by the school before the submission of the final copy.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her heartfelt thanks to everyone who helped make this study possible. She is especially grateful to Dr. Revina O. Mendoza her mentor, for generously sharing her time, expertise, and wisdom, and for continuously encouraging the researcher to complete this work. She also sincerely thanks Dr. Judith C. Chavez, Dr. Miguela B. Napiere, Dr. Maria Alona A. Galendez, and Dr. Kriscentti Exzur P. Barcelona esteemed members of the panel, for their insightful comments, intellectual expertise, and valuable suggestions that greatly improved this paper. She also extends her thanks to Dr. Ralph Jay Magsalay for his help with the statistical analysis and checking of the data. The researcher is also grateful to the participants of the study for giving their time and cooperation, which made this research possible.

REFERENCES

- Bhandari, P. (2021). Descriptive-correlational design in research: Measuring variable associations and making informed predictions. *International Journal of Research Methods*, 12(3), 157–169.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *The ecology of human development: Experiments by nature and design*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Busalla, H. A., & Mendoza, R. O. (2024). Parents' engagement in home-based activities and teachers' emotional availability: implications on kindergartners' learning skills. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(5), 2216–2225. <https://doi.org/10.17613/f9kq-q647>
- Buvanewari, B., & Padakannaya, P. (2017). Development of a home literacy environment questionnaire for Tamil-speaking kindergarten children. *Language Testing in Asia*, 7(1), 14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40468-017-0047-y>
- Claes, R., Laga, J., Denies, K., Bleukx, N., Dockx, J., Van Keer, H., & Aesaert, K. (2024). The interplay between students' home literacy environment, reading attitudes and comprehension: a serial mediation analysis using PIRLS 2021-data. *Large-scale Assessments in Education*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40536-024-00233-8>
- Department of Education. (2023). *MATATAG Kindergarten Curriculum Guide* [PDF file]. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/matatag-curriculum/matatag-kindergarten-cg/>

- Dowdall, N., Melendez-Torres, G. J., Murray, L., Gardner, F., Hartford, L., & Cooper, P. J. (2020). Shared picture book reading interventions for child language development: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Child Development*, 91(2), e383–e399. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13225>
- Garcia-Peinado, R. (2023). The impact of classroom climate on emotional development in childhood. *Environment and Social Psychology*, 9 (1). <https://doi.org/10.54517/esp.v9i1.1868>
- Goodrich, J. M., C. J. Lonigan, B. M. Phillips, J. M. Farver, and K. D. Wilson. (2021). “Influences of the home language and literacy environment on Spanish and English vocabulary growth among dual language learners.” *Early Childhood Research Quarterly* 57:27–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2021.05.002>
- Grolig L (2020) Shared Storybook Reading and Oral Language Development: A Bioecological Perspective. *Front. Psychol.* 11:1818. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01818
- Hasanah, A. I., Mahmud, M., & Salija, K. (2022). The implementation of storytelling method to improve students’ speaking achievement. *Pinisi Journal of Art, Humanity and Social*, 2(5), 116–125.
- Hu, L., & Bentler, P. M. (1999). Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>
- Khan, K. S., Logan, J., Justice, L. M., Bowles, R. P., & Piasta, S. B. (2021). The contribution of vocabulary, grammar, and phonological awareness across a continuum of narrative ability levels in young children. *Journal of Speech Language and Hearing Research*, 64(9), 3489–3503. https://doi.org/10.1044/2021_jslhr-20-00403
- Li, X. (2025). Preschool children’s oral narrative abilities. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 15(2), 70–83. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-1502017083>
- National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research. (1979). The Belmont report: Ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of human subjects of research. <https://www.hhs.gov/ohrp/regulations-and-policy/belmont-report/index.html>
- Nicolopoulou, A., Schnabel Cortina, K., Ilgaz, H., Cates, C. B., & de Sá, A. B. (2021). Using storytelling and story acting to promote oral language development in early childhood classrooms. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 55, 312–326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2020.10.002>
- Niklas F, Wirth A, Guffler S, Drescher N and Ehmig SC (2020) The Home Literacy Environment as a Mediator Between Parental Attitudes Toward Shared Reading and Children’s Linguistic Competencies. *Front. Psychol.* 11:1628. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.01628
- Nishonova, D. (2021). Importance of storytelling technique in teaching English language. *Current in Philology*, 4(4), 1–4. <https://presedu.jspi.uz/index.php/ruslit/article/download/2355/1549>
- Noddings, N. (1984). *Caring: A feminine approach to ethics and moral education*. University of California Press.
- Quan, Q., Gao, Y., & Wang, Q. (2025). The impact of teacher emotional support on students’ engagement in AI-mediated English learning environments: The mediating role of resilience and self-efficacy. *Acta Psychologica*, 260, 105766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2025.105766>
- Rankin, P. S., Staton, S., Potia, A. H., Houen, S., & Thorpe, K. (2022). Emotional quality of early education programs improves language learning: A within-child across context design. *Child development*, 93(6), 1680–1697. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13811>

- Ratih, G. K., Iriani, A., & Dwikurnaningsih, Y. (2022). Kindergarten teachers training in integrating anti-corruption education through storytelling and game. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini [Journal of Obsession: Journal of Early Childhood Education]*, 6(3), 1628-1639. <https://doi.org/10.31004/obsesi.v6i13.1806>
- Simatupang, N. D., Sholichah, S. A., & Simanjuntak, I. A. (2025). Improving Early Literacy Through Kamishibai Storytelling: Action Research in an Indonesian Kindergarten. *Golden Age Jurnal Ilmiah Tumbuh Kembang Anak Usia Dini*, 10(1), 101–113. <https://doi.org/10.14421/jga.2025.101-08>
- van Huisstede, L., Marley, S. C., Bernstein, K. A., Pierce-Rivera, M., Schmidt, A., Millinger, J., Kelley, M. F., Restrepo, M. A., & Vargas Cesario, C. (2026). Drama during story time supports preschoolers' understanding of story character feeling states. *Journal of Early Childhood Literacy*, 26(1), 83-110.
- Vieta, T. Q., & Nhib, T. Y. (2024). Integrating theatrical arts into storytelling instruction in primary education: A theoretical framework and practical applications. *International Electronic Journal of Elementary Education*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.26822/iejee.2024.369>
- Vretudaki, H. (2021). Enhancing preschoolers' understanding about story structure. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 9(9), 634–644. <https://doi.org/10.31686/ijer.vol9.iss9.3340>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: the development of higher psychological processes* (M. Cole, V. Jolm-Steiner, S. Scribner, & E. Souberman, Eds.). Harvard University Press.
- Wang X (2023). Exploring positive teacher-student relationships: the synergy of teacher mindfulness and emotional intelligence. *Front. Psychol.* 14:1301786. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1301786
- Xing, L., Tang, Y., Liu, Q., Chen, H., Zeng, J., & Su, J. (2025). The effects of interactive reading on young children's narrative abilities: a meta-analytic study. *Frontiers in psychology*, 16, 1653511. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1653511>
- Yang, N., Shi, J., Lu, J. and Huang, Y. (2021) Language development in early childhood: quality of teacher-child interaction and children's receptive vocabulary competency. *Front. Psychol.* 12:649680. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2021.649680